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“Teaching methods of listening comprehension”

Annotation: *This article named “Methods of Teaching Listening Comprehension” outlines methods, strategies, resources, and principles for improving students' listening comprehension skills. It will provide future teachers with the materials they need to know, what the concept of listening teaching means and how to teach students to listen in English.*

Key words: *stress, rhythm , pause, linguistic , pragmatic, paralinguistic ,authentic, perception, integration, synthesis.*

Listening is receiving language through the ears. Listening involves identifying the sounds of speech and processing them into words and sentences. When we listen, we use our ears to receive individual sounds (letters, stress, rhythm and pauses) and we use our brain to convert these into messages that mean something to us.

Listening in any language requires focus and attention. It is a skill that some people need to work at harder than others. People who have difficulty concentrating are typically poor listeners. Listening in a second language requires even greater focus.

Like babies, we learn this skill by listening to people who already know how to speak the language. This may or may not include native speakers. For practice, you can listen to live or recorded voices. The most important thing is to listen to a variety of voices as often as you can.

Listening is the first of the four language skills, which are:

-Listening

-Speaking

-Reading

-Writing

In our own language, listening is usually the first language skill that we learn.

To become a fluent speaker in English, you need to develop strong listening skills. Listening not only helps you understand what people are saying to you. It also helps you to speak clearly to other people. It helps you learn how to pronounce words properly, how to use intonation, and where to place stress in words and

sentences. This makes your speech easier for other people **listening to you** to understand!

For our purposes, we can define listening as the process whereby orally

communicated messages are attended to, recognized, and interpreted in light of needs and experiences, and stored for future use. This definition emphasizes that when we listen we assign meaning to stimuli and that in assigning meaning we are influenced by prior habits, expectations, and desires. Listening, then, is an active, creative process governed by the listener's inner state.

In order to define listening, we must outline the main component skills in listening. In terms of the necessary components, we can list the following:

- discrimination between sounds
- recognizing words
- identifying grammatical groupings of words
- identifying 'pragmatic units' - expressions and sets of utterance which function as whole units to create meaning
- connecting linguistic cues to paralinguistic cues (intonation and stress) and to nonlinguistic cues (gestures and relevant objects in the situation) in order to construct meaning
- using background knowledge (what we already know about the content and the form) and context (what has already been said) to predict and then to confirm meaning
- recalling important words and ideas

Successful listening involves an integration of these component skills. In this sense, listening is a coordination of the component skills, not the individual skills themselves. This integration of these perception skills, analysis skills, and synthesis skills is what we call a person's *listening ability*

Even though a person may have good listening ability, he or she may not always be able to understand what is being said. In order to understand messages, some conscious action is necessary to use this ability effectively, so it is not possible to view it directly, but we can see the effects of this action. The underlying action for successful listening is *decision making*. The listener must make these kinds of decisions:

- What kind of situation is this?
- What is my plan for listening?
- What are the important words and units of meaning?
- Does the message make sense?

Successful listening requires making effective 'real time' decisions about these questions. In this sense, listening is primarily a thinking process - *thinking about meaning* . Effective listeners develop a useful way of thinking about meaning as they listen. The way in which listener makes these decisions is what we will call a *listening strategy*

Listening strategies are techniques or activities that contribute directly to the comprehension and recall of listening input. Listening strategies can be classified by how the listener processes the input.

Top-down strategies are listener based; the listener taps into background knowledge of the topic, the situation or context, the type of text, and the language. This

background knowledge activates a set of expectations that help the listener to interpret what is heard and anticipate what will come next. Top-down strategies include

- listening for the main idea
- predicting
- drawing inferences
- summarizing

Bottom-up strategies are text based; the listener relies on the language in the message, that is, the combination of sounds, words, and grammar that creates meaning. Bottom-up strategies include

- listening for specific details
- recognizing cognates
- recognizing word-order patterns

Strategic listeners also use metacognitive strategies to plan, monitor, and evaluate their listening.

-They plan by deciding which listening strategies will serve best in a particular situation.

-They monitor their comprehension and the effectiveness of the selected strategies.

-They evaluate by determining whether they have achieved their listening comprehension goals and whether the combination of listening strategies selected was an effective one.

Pre-listening Strategies

You might get ready to listen by thinking about:

- The speaker and the speaker's purpose: Who is the speaker? What do you think they want you to know or do?

- Your purpose for listening: What do you want? To find out specific information? The gist? The speaker's mood? To support the speaker?

- Your knowledge/experience: Think about what you already know about the subject, the situation, and the language you will be hearing

- How you would listen in your native language: How would you make sure you understood? How

would you listen actively?

- Limiting or removing distractions

Predict what you will be hearing by considering:

- The language you will hear: key words or phrases, the grammar tenses, etc.

- The information or opinions you expect to hear

While-listening Strategies

While you listen you'll need to use strategies to comprehend:

- Use visual clues to help you understand: the setting, body language, facial expressions

- Do targeted listening for specific information

- Listen for key words that you know

- Listen for clues (verb endings, intonation, sequence words) that help you understand

- Take notes to help you organize and remember what you hear
- Pause periodically to ask yourself, “Does this make sense to me?”
- Decide what is and is not important to understand; what you can “skip”
- Ask for help if you do not understand
- Ask for clarification or repetition from the speaker or ask if what you understood

is correct

- Ask additional questions to flesh out your understanding

Post-listening Strategies

After you listen these strategies might help you synthesize, interpret and evaluate what you’ve heard:

- See if you can restate, paraphrase, or summarize what you heard
- Consider what you heard and how it fits with what you know
- Check the accuracy of your predictions
- Discuss or respond to what you heard through writing, drawing, drama, etc.
- Identify facts vs. opinions, more and less important details, supported vs. unsupported ideas

do

- Decide whether your listening purpose has been met and what else you need to do
- Think about the process and strategies you used to listen – which worked well?

Listening material

The content of the material also influences comprehension. The following factors should be taken into consideration when selecting the material for auding:

The topic of communication: whether it is within the ability of the pupils to understand, and what difficulties pupils will come across (proper names, geographical names, terminology, etc). The type of communication: whether it is a description or a narration. Description as a type of communication is less emotional and interesting, that is why it is difficult for the teacher to arouse pupils' interest in auding such a text. Narration is more interesting for auding. Consequently, this type of communication should be used for listening comprehension. The context and pupils' readiness (intellectual and situational) to understand it. The way the narrative progresses: whether the passage is taken from the beginning of a story, the nucleus of the story, the progress of the action or, finally, the end of the story. The title of the story may be helpful in comprehending the main idea of the text. The simpler the narrative progresses, the better it is for developing pupils' skills in auding. The form of communication: whether the text is a dialogue or a monologue. Monologic speech is easier for the learners, therefore, it is preferable for developing pupils' listening ability

Conditions of presenting the material are of great importance for teaching auding, namely:

- the speed of the speech the pupil is auditing. The hearer cannot change the speed of the speaker;

- there are different points of view on the problem of the speed of speech in teaching auditing a foreign language.

Consequently, in teaching listening comprehension the teacher should bear in mind all the difficulties pupils encounter when auditing in a foreign language. To fulfill the task the teacher must train his pupils in listening comprehension beginning with the first lesson and throughout the whole period of instruction. These are the techniques the teacher uses for the purpose:

The teacher uses the foreign language:

- when giving the class instructions;
- when presenting new language material (words, sentence patterns);
- when checking pupils' comprehension;
- when consolidating the material presented;
- when checking pupils' assimilation of the language material covered.

These are the cases when the target language is used as a means of communication and a means of teaching. There is a great deal of auditing in all the points of the

lesson. This raises the problem of the teacher's speech during the lesson. It should be correct, sufficiently loud, clear, and expressive. But many of the teachers are too talkative. We can hear them speaking most of the time. Moreover, some teachers speak a great deal in their native languages. Conducting a lesson in a foreign language gives the teacher an opportunity to develop pupils' abilities in hearing; to train them in listening to him attentively during the lesson; to demonstrate the language as a means of communication; to provide favorable conditions for the assimilation of the language; to perfect his own speaking skills; to keep his own speech under control, i. e., to keep himself from undue talkativeness.

The teacher uses drill and speech exercises for developing listening comprehension. We can group drill exercises into exercises designed for overcoming linguistic difficulties, and exercises which can eliminate psychological difficulties.

The first group of drill exercises includes:

Phonetic exercises which will help the teacher to develop his pupils' ear for English sounds;

- listen to the following words and raise your hands when you hear the words with [ae] (The teacher says: desk, pen, ten, bag, etc.);

- listen to the following pairs of words and say in what sound they differ: pen -- pin; bed -- bad; eyes -- ice; white -- wide.

Lexical exercises which will help the teacher to develop pupils' skills in recognizing words:

- listen to the words and recognize the word "boy" among other words: a baby, a toy, a boat, a boy, a girl;

- listen to the following words and raise your hands when you hear the words referring to plants: street, tree, grass, class, flower, and tower;

- listen to the following sentences and say whether the word country has the same meaning in both sentences:

I usually spent my holidays in the country.

Grammar exercises which help the teacher to develop pupils' skills in recognizing grammar forms and structures:

- listen to the following words and raise your hands when you hear words in plural: desk, tables, book, box, pens, books, boxes, etc.;

- listen to the following sentences and say in which one the word help is used as a noun. He can help you. I need his help.

The second group of drill exercises includes:

1. Exercises which help the teacher to develop his pupils' auditory memory:

- listen to the following words and try to memorize them. (The teacher pronounces a number of words pointing to the object each denotes: a carrot, a potato, a cucumber, a tomato. Afterwards pupils are told to point to the object the teacher names.);

- listen to the phrases and repeat them. The teacher says: on the table, in the box, near the blackboard;

- listen to the sentences and repeat them. (The teacher says: I like tea. Ann doesn't like tea. She likes milk.);

- listen to the sentences and repeat them in the same sequence. (The teacher says: In the evening we have tea. I like it very much. The teacher may increase the number of sentences for pupils to memorize.).

2. Exercises which are designed for developing pupils' attention:

- listen to the following text: I have a sister. Her name is Ann. Mike has no sister. He has a brother.

- Now say what is the name of Mike's sister is.

- listen to the text. (The text follows.) Now say which sentence was omitted (added) when you listened to it a second time.

3. Exercises which develop pupils' visual imagination:

- listen to the following definition and give it a name: We write with it on the blackboard. We take it when it rains.

- listen and say which season it is: It is cold. It often snows. Children can skate and ski.

4. Exercises which help the teacher to develop his pupils' logical thinking:

- listen to the sentences and say whether they are logically arranged: Her name is Mary. This is a girl.

Drill exercises are quite indispensable to developing pupils' skills in listening comprehension. Speech exercises are designed for developing pupils' skills in auditing. Several groups of exercises may be suggested:

a) Exercises which teach pupils to understand texts different in content, form, and type. Pupils are asked to listen to a description or a narration; the text may be a dialogue, it may deal with the life of people whose language the pupils study, or with the pupils' environment:

- listen to the story. Your task is to define its main idea. You should choose one among those suggested by the teacher;

- listen to the story. Your task is to grasp as much information as you can. While auditing try to put down key words and sentences; they will help you to convey the context of the story.

The usage of the authentic listening material is one of the problems in the teaching listening comprehension. The important point, as always, is to meet the needs of the learners. On the short-term basis the learners need to listen to material, which allows them to feel comfortable, perhaps because it is mainly recycling known

language. In addition to this, particularly taking their long-term needs into account, the learners have to be exposed to listening material, which is beyond their productive level. Whether this is 'authentic' in the early stages is not entirely relevant provided the material gets them used to *not understanding* every word; encourages them to *guess* - and, over and above this, stimulates them to talk (or read or write, if these are following-up activities). But, of course, whenever

possible, some authentic material should be used, and on an increasing scale as the course progresses. However, it must be kept in mind that the use of authentic

material for listening is very different from reading, where, because the learners can work individually and at their own pace, authentic material carries fewer risks. In the typical listening situation, care has to be taken to see that learners are not

discouraged by excessive difficulties. In general, authentic materials are best used where the learners themselves are likely to appreciate them and accept them in spite of difficulties.

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